

Nagpur Metro Indicator

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ABSTRACT

An increase in population has led to the growth of traffic in India. To ease the traffic situation in the country and make travel convenient for the people, the government has introduced the metro rail in many cities. It is a cheap mode of travel, which helps in reducing the energy consumption, is eco-friendly, and is the reason behind the prevention of accidents. The modern design of metro coaches, the stylish appearance of metro stations, and superior comfort facilities are some of the reasons why metro is becoming popular in India.

KEYWORDS: Nagpur Metro, Fare, Routes, Timetable, Stations

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INTRODUCTION

This is an integrated service which provide all information about the metro rail and it's routes for public. The proposed system is an android based application which provides information regarding timings, routes, fare. This system manages public feedback about services through it's complaint management system. There is also an admin module where admin can add stations, trains, routes and also update the fares. The admin is a panel consisting of a group of authorized persons. Efficient, safe and secure transportation networks are the foundation of all modern cities' development and substantiality. The most sought-after intelligent solutions refers to the deployment of mobile computing and connectivity in every part of an interconnected transportation system;

LITERATURE REVIEW

A. DELHI METRO RAIL

A metro rail-based system was prescribed by RITES, containing a network of surface, underground and raised corridors accumulating to 213 kms, to stay aware of the traffic demand up to the year 2021. The entire task expense was assessed at Rs. 15000 Crores according to 1996 value level. The system at present handles 2.4 million commuters daily. The first and second phases of Delhi metro have been finished. The DMRC site demonstrates various advantages of metro. These are: time spared by the workers, Reduction in accidents, reduced fuel consumption, dependable and safe travel, reduced atmospheric pollution, reduced operating

expense of vehicles and increase in the normal vehicular speed. This paper exhibits an assessment and analysis of the advantages asserted by the Delhi metro. Comparable advantages were additionally expected during the planning phases of Kolkata and Chennai metro rail systems. Nonetheless, the execution of metro system in both these urban communities has not satisfied the desires.

B. CHENNAI METRO RAIL

S.Vydhianathan (2003) discussed the initially elevated metro rail transport system in Chennai. The metro system has advanced stations comforts, elevators at platforms, lifts for the crippled and the aged. Chennai MRTS ought to be the most appealing travel choice in a metro city that has more than 20 lakh vehicles out and about, congested driving conditions, number of mishaps recorded and rising air contamination. In spite, there are rare commuters in a three-coach train and the stations remain deserted – its as if the city has for all intents and purposes denied its presence. In spite of the speculation of Rs.20,000 crores, there are no obvious positive returns. Commuters declines to increase, however the local city transports run packed. The time is fortunate to at the end of the day audit the whole approach towards urban transportation issues and concoct a joined methodology towards a rail and road system. Numerous reasons have been credited to the Chennai Metro Rail Transit System as yet remaining a non-starter. The two key reasons appear to have been the higher fare structure furthermore

the absence of feeder transportation facilities at the stations in the first stage.

C. KOLKATA METRO RAIL

The Kolkata metro railway is the principal ever underground rail line venture actualized in India. The normal weekday travel trips assessed on 1971 were around 46 lakhs, which were projected to increase to 53 lakhs in 1976, 67 lakhs in 1983 and 83 lakhs in 1990, as per the reports on Kolkata Mass Transit Study, arranged in 1971. Singh (2002) presents a year-wise total working expenditures and total traffic profit of the metro railroad. The normal commuter activity in 1978 after the opening of the main stage was required to be around 46.9 crore travellers yearly and in 1990 to be around 61.25 crore travellers. The yearly commuters volume estimation was to be 62.37 crore by 2000. The quantity of beginning travellers successfully utilizing the metro railroad amid the period 1999-2000 was just 5.58 crore, which is well beneath, roughly one-eleventh of what the evaluated activity was by the year 1990. Low traffic is essentially because of one of the primary reasons of the metro rail as yet being unviable. The system which was initially assessed to be finished inside an expense of Rs. 140 crores was in the end finished at the expense of Rs. 1600 crores.

PROBLEM DEFINITION

The problem occurred before having online system includes:

1. File lost When online system is not implemented the complaints are reported in files. The files are always lost due to some human errors.
2. Most updations are unnoticeable.

EVALUATION CRITERIA

The system helps to make a complaint online, display metro timetable, fares and route maps. Users can register complaints through the site. Users can view metro timetable. User can also view the fare details and the route map. An admin login page where admin can add stations, trains, routes, update fare.

Admin

Figure1-Admin Module

This feature allows the admin to view and reply to complaints. Admin can add stations, route, train. Admin can also add and update fare details, and even add a new admin. Actually, the admin is a panel consisting of a group of authorized persons.

Functional Requirements

The system must allow admin to add train, station, routes, fare, metro timetable and even add a new admin.

The system must also allow admin to reply to the complaints send by the user.

The system should be designed in such a way that only authorized people should be allowed to access some particular modules.

The records should be modified by only administrators and no one else.

Figure 2- Metro time table

This module contains various facilities like view time chart between two stations. This feature allows the users to view the metro timetable. Users are required to enter the source station and destination station, when they enter the data then the system will show the metro time table.

Functional Requirements

System must allow the users to enter the source station and destination stations.

System must be able to process information from database.

Figure 3-Fare and route map module

This module contains various facilities like display fare and display route map. This feature allows the users to view the fare and route map. Users are required to enter the source and destination station, when they enter the data then the system will display fare details and the route map.

Functional Requirements

System must allow the users to enter the source and destination stations.

System must be able to retrieve information from the database.

CONCLUSION

The system has been developed with much care and free of errors and at the same time it is efficient and less time-consuming. The purpose of this project was to develop a web application for metro rail management. This project helped us in gaining valuable information and practical knowledge

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